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Authors:	Ramaz Kvatadze (GRENA), Kamila Duvanaeva (GEANT), Eleonora Parisi (LifeWatch ERIC), Chris Atherton (GEANT)
Internal Reviewers:	Matias Barberis (EFIS), Frederik Tilman (GFZ)

Abstract

This deliverable is the final report on the stakeholder engagement and outreach activities performed within the frame of SUBMERSE project. The report is related to Work Package 4 Communication, Exploitation and Impact. The stakeholder engagement was essential for the successful implementation of the project objectives. It provides an overview of the stakeholders' landscape, description of various engagement channels and presents qualitative and quantitative results of the performed work.

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Executive Summary

The aim of the SUBMERSE project was to prepare and deploy research instruments Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SoP) in several geographically diverse locations for the fibre sensing purposes and disseminate generated data to the relevant research communities. These technologies enable continuous sensing along optical fibres and allow the collection of valuable geophysical and environmental data across large geographic areas.

Fibre optic sensing represents a rapidly developing technological field with significant scientific and societal potential. The technology enables monitoring of critical infrastructure such as telecommunication networks, oil and gas pipelines and civil engineering structures, while also providing new capabilities for Earth science research. In particular, fibre sensing contributes to the study of ocean dynamics, seismology, marine volcanology, climate processes and environmental hazards, including early warning systems for earthquakes and tsunamis.

An important step in the development of fibre sensing was made by the implementation of this technology in the already deployed telecommunication cables. This approach significantly reduces deployment costs and environmental impact while improving sustainability and scalability of sensing systems. Since fibre optic sensing systems may detect signals related to sensitive infrastructure activity, including vessel movements or cable disturbances, cooperation with national security authorities is essential before releasing collected data to the scientific community.

The goal of the **stakeholder engagement and outreach activities** was to contribute to the implementation of project objectives and maximise its visibility, usability and long-term impact of the project results. For this reason, stakeholder engagement and outreach plan was developed at the beginning of the project. Communication and dissemination are preconditions for successful stakeholder engagement. Thus, taking into account the wide range of potential stakeholders and their different interest, Task 4.2 Stakeholder Engagement and Outreach was working in close cooperation with Task 4.1 Communications and Dissemination and with all work packages of the project.

The following activities were performed for identifying and engaging with stakeholders:

- Stakeholder identification – the individuals and/or organizations who have an interest in the results obtained by the project and potential users of the generated data.
- Stakeholder mapping - identify the role of each stakeholder or group, how they can contribute to the success and sustainability of the project.
- Defining most effective communication and outreach channels appropriate to each stakeholder groups.
- Conducting and regularly reviewing the engagement activities, analysing lessons learned and if needed revising the plan for further improvement.

The project identified and engaged a wide range of stakeholders including research organisations, fibre sensing technology developers, submarine cable operators, national research and education networks, public authorities and international scientific initiatives. Engagement activities included targeted communication, participation in conferences and workshops, collaboration with related projects, dissemination of scientific publications and organisation of training and knowledge sharing activities.

This deliverable summarises the stakeholder landscape relevant to the project, the engagement channels used and the results of outreach activities performed during the project. The report demonstrates how stakeholder engagement supported the dissemination of project outcomes and strengthened collaboration between scientific communities, technology and communication infrastructure providers.

1 Introduction

The final report on stakeholder engagement and outreach of the SUBMERSE project describes the identification and mapping of stakeholders, different engagement channels used and engagement activities performed during the implementation of the project. Task 4.2 worked in close cooperation with all work packages to identify and map stakeholders and establish effective and suitable communication channels for each group of stakeholders that will maximise visibility and outcomes of the project.

The two main objectives of the SUBMERSE project were as follows:

- Deployment of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) instruments at project participants' sites in Norway, Greece and Portugal and the production of pre-processed datasets from the generated data.
- Using machine learning algorithms made pre-processed data accessible for different research communities and supporting its integration into the European data space via European Open Science Cloud EOSC, Destination Earth and Copernicus programmes.

In addition, training and capacity building activities were planned for enhancing the collection, processing and use of the generated data by the project internal staff, as well as by the external stakeholders interested in integrating produced datasets into their scientific workflows.

This report is based on the deliverable D4.2 Stakeholder engagement and outreach plan developed at the beginning of the project and adjusted during project implementation. The main objective was to identify relevant stakeholders, make them aware of concerning outcomes of the project in terms of used technology solutions and generated and processed FAIR-compliant datasets. For this reason, the following types of the stakeholders were considered for cooperation:

- **Research organisations** working in the geosciences and marine sciences as well as in other related scientific fields such as climate change or in the development of fibre optic sensing techniques, fibre sensing equipment manufacturers, companies providing submarine cable system services, and national research and education networks (NRENs), which provide connectivity to the research communities, etc.
- Another segment of **potential stakeholders** which can benefit from obtained information (data) by the project are national security authorities, earthquake monitoring agencies, tsunami warning centres for monitoring purposes; European, regional and national institutions for infrastructure development and funding.

The deliverable describes the stakeholder engagement and outreach final report consisting of introduction (Section 1), stakeholder identification and mapping (Section 2), different engagement channels exploited by the project (Section 3). The final section 4 draws some conclusions.

2 Stakeholder identification and mapping

Stakeholder identification and mapping is an important step in understanding who the stakeholders are, what interests and expertise do they have and how can they contribute to the project. Communicated information and engagement channels were carefully selected for each group of stakeholders to increase potential impact. The objective of this activity was to ensure that stakeholders are continuously up to date with the SUBMERSE project progress. Another important objective was to support the relevant research communities in usage of the datasets generated by the research instruments in their scientific work that was achieved by knowledge sharing and training. Equally important was regular communication with fibre sensing equipment developer companies and submarine cable system service providers to facilitate development and implementation of this technology.

Figure 1. SUBMERSE Stakeholder's groups

The project involves a wide range of **internal and external stakeholders**:

Internal stakeholders include the Project Advisory Board, project management, work package leaders, task leaders, and all project participants, as well as partner research organisations and infrastructure service provider organisations.

External stakeholders encompass several groups. Within research communities, this includes seismology, oceanography, marine volcanology and tsunami studies, and marine biology, including cetology. On the technology side, stakeholders include fibre sensing system developers, submarine cable system operators and

developers, and National Research and Education Networks (NRENs). Additional external stakeholders include relevant projects referenced in section 3.5, national security authorities in participating countries, and national agencies such as earthquake monitoring agencies and tsunami warning centres. The project also engages with the European Commission and EU research infrastructures and initiatives, including the European Plate Observing System (EPOS-ERIC), the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), LifeWatch ERIC, and the e-Infrastructure Reflection Group (e-IRG). Furthermore, international organisations such as the International Cable Protection Committee (ICPC), the Group on Earth Observations (GEO), the International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG), the European Geosciences Union (EGU), and the European Seismological Commission (ESC) are key stakeholders, alongside the general public.

Table 1. Role of different stakeholder groups in the project

Stakeholders	Role in the project
Internal stakeholders	Implementation of the project
Research communities	Analysis of the data obtained by the project
Technology side	Fibre sensing equipment manufacturers – cooperation for the further development of the technology Submarine cable system operators and NRENs – support in implementation of fibre sensing in their infrastructures
Relevant projects	Knowledge sharing and collaboration
National security authorities in project participant countries	Cooperation and filtering sensitive data before releasing collected data to the scientific communities
Relevant national agencies e.g. earthquake monitoring agencies, tsunami warning centres, etc.	Cooperation with project participant organizations providing fibre sensing for research and monitoring
European Commission	Review of project results and support in further developments in this field
EU Research Infrastructures and related initiatives	Providing computational and storage resources for analysis of obtained datasets, dissemination
International organisations	Dissemination and support in effective usage of generated data
General public	Dissemination capabilities of fibre sensing technology in various fields of Earth science and infrastructure monitoring

3 Stakeholder engagement channels

3.1 Engagement channels and usage

SUBMERSE project used the following engagement channels to reach, inform and develop cooperation with stakeholders: project website, social media, publications, presentations at conferences and workshops, specific project-led workshops and trainings as well as providing access to generated datasets.

Considering the wide range of stakeholder types and different aims for engagement project defined various communication channels and content for each group. The table below presents engagement channels used to reach various target groups.

Table 2. Usage of various engagement channels for targeted audiences

Stakeholder groups	Project website	Social media	Scientific publications	Scientific events	Workshops and trainings	Access to datasets
Internal stakeholders	+	+	+	+	+	+
Research communities	+	+	+	+	+	+
Technology side	+	+	+	+	+	+
Relevant projects	+	+	+	+	+	+
National security authorities	+	+				+
Relevant national agencies	+	+	+			
European Commission	+	+		+		
EU RIs and related initiatives	+	+		+		
International organisations	+	+		+		
General public	+	+				

Engagement activities were carefully analysed during monthly Project Management Board (PMB) and work package 4 meetings. Communication and engagement activities were also presented and discussed at Project

Advisory Board meetings. For the implementation of stakeholder engagement and outreach activities and to communicate the findings with the stakeholders' close collaboration between all work packages was necessary. Results obtained in the course of each engagement channel were discussed and if needed additional actions were implemented, as described below.

3.1.1 Project website and social media

The project website <https://submerse.eu/> was launched at the beginning of the project. It is the central instrument for dissemination of information concerning activities and progress of the SUBMERSE. The website provides a short description of the project, information about data collection sites, used fibre sensing technologies and use cases, as well as project related news and events. Various information levels take into account different stakeholder needs. The website itself is updated on a regular basis, and project participants are contributing with material to the website which is managed and maintained by Task 4.1. It is planned to maintain website after the end of the project to add project-based publications.

Originally, a Twitter/X account <https://x.com/SUBMERSEproject> was registered. However, following the changes resulting from the takeover, many scientists and other stakeholders abandoned X, and an alternative science-friendly social-media platform had to be identified to focus dissemination efforts on. Considering that LinkedIn offers great potential for professional networking and would help to expand the project audience it was decided to move to this platform <https://www.linkedin.com/company/submerse-project/>. Currently LinkedIn channel has over 875 followers and contains information about project activities including images and videos.

3.1.2 Publications and datasets

Publishing scientific papers is essential to raise awareness about the project within scientific community and core stakeholders working within this technology field. Several research publications were prepared in course of project implementation. The full list of publications is available under F&T Portal, as part of the project reporting.

Important objectives of the project are the production of datasets and relevant software that will be used by the research community to analyse generated data. For this reason, following work has been performed:

- Dataset: Afonso Loureiro, GeoLab, GFZ Data Services, Dataset/DAS, [doi:10.14470/8K802502](https://doi.org/10.14470/8K802502).
- Software:
 - OptoDas plugin for Seedlink server(<https://github.com/SeisComp/seedlink>),
 - SSA2py (<https://github.com/ifountoul/SSA2py>) is an open-source Python project for Source-Scanning Algorithm (SSA),
 - DeeSubDAS software is distributed as supplementary material to the corresponding paper. It is also integrated into the popular SeisBench platform <https://github.com/seisbench/seisbench/releases/tag/v0.11.0>,
 - SUBMERSE is a Python-based toolbox for Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) <https://submerse.gitlab-pages.pccss.pl/submerse/>.

3.1.3 Presentations and knowledge-sharing at conferences and workshops

To keep up the engagement with the scientific community, presentations and knowledge sharing at conferences and workshops were the usual channels, fostering expanding contacts and developing cooperation with potential stakeholders. At the beginning of the project an internal document was created to identify relevant workshops and conferences for presentation and dissemination of project results. This document was regularly updated. The following topics of the external events were considered important for the participation:

- Using fibre sensing for research in various fields of Earth science,
- Monitoring of health and security of infrastructures,
- Fibre sensing technology development and its deployment in submarine cable systems.

Conferences and workshops organised with participation of the project partners were also used to present project results. For example, GEANT TNC research and education networking conference, NORDUNET conference and workshop, among others.

The following table presents information about conferences and workshops with participation of SUBMERSE partners. In total project representatives participated in 43 international events and made 37 presentations. Table below presents more detailed information about events and types of SUBMERSE project participation.

Table 3. Project presence at conferences and workshops

No	Name of the event	Dates	Location	Focus/target stakeholders	Type of attendance
1	European Workshop on Optical Fibre Sensors EWOFS 2023	23-26 May 2023	Mons, Belgium	Optical fibre sensors	1 presentation
2	TNC23	5-9 June 2023	Tirana, Albania	NRENs, researchers	4 participants
3	OPTOEL 2023	14-16 June 2023	Seville, Spain	Optoelectronics	2 participants, 2 moderators
4	International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics IUGG	11-20 July 2023	Berlin, Germany	Geoscientists, including oceanography	1 presentation
5	OPTICA Optical Sensors	30 July-03 August 2023	Munich, Germany	Optical sensors	1 presentation, 3 participants
6	28th International Conference on Optical Fiber Sensors	20-24 November 2023	Hamamatsu, Japan	Optical Fiber Sensors	1 presentation, 3 participants

No	Name of the event	Dates	Location	Focus/target stakeholders	Type of attendance
7	e-Infrastructure Reflection Group e-IRG workshop	30 November-1 December 2023	Valencia, Spain	e-Infrastructures	4 participants
8	American Geophysical Union AGU	11-15 December 2023	San Francisco, CA USA	Geophysical applications	1 participant
9	European Geosciences Union EGU	14-19 April 2024	Vienna, Austria	Geoscientists, including oceanography	1 presentation, 1 poster
10	Seismological Society of America SSA	29 April-3 May 2024	Anchorage, USA	Seismologists	1 presentation, 1 poster
11	Submarine Networks EMEA	29-30 May 2024	London, UK	Subsea cable owners, operators, investors, wholesalers	panel on Sensing Technologies
12	TNC24	10-14 June 2024	Rennes, France	NRENS	2 presentations, moderator
13	International School on Light Sciences and Technologies (ISLiST 2024)	16-20 June 2024	Santander, Spain	Light Technologies	1 presentation
14	Galileo conference on Fibre Optic Sensing in Geosciences	16-20 June 2024	Catania, Italy	Geoscientists employing fibre optic sensing	1 presentation
15	OPTICA Sensing Congress	15-19 July 2024	Toulouse, France	Optical sensors	3 participants
16	The 6th International Conference on Application of Optics and Photonics (AOP) 2024	16 -19 July 2024	Aveiro, Portugal	Application of Optics and Photonics	1 plenary session
17	2024 IEEE Sensors Applications Symposium	23-25 July 2024	Naples, Italy	Applications of sensors	1 participant
18	CTBTO	9-11 September 2024	Vienna, Austria	Ocean observatories, acoustic sensor technologies, etc.	1 participant
19	NORDUnet Conference 2024	10-12 September 2024	Bergen, Norway	Research and education community	1 presentation, 2 participants

No	Name of the event	Dates	Location	Focus/target stakeholders	Type of attendance
20	DGG Arbeitskreis Seismologie	16-19 September 2024	Hamburg, Germany	Seismologists	1 presentation, 2 participants
21	European Seismological Commission ESC	22-27 September 2024	Corfu, Greece	Seismologists	2 participants
22	Atlantic Convergence	1-3 October 2024	Lisbon, Portugal	Subsea, Data center, IX, Official bodies	1 presentation, panel
23	Seismological Society of America SSA	7-10 October 2024	Vancouver, BC	Seismological applications of fibre-optic cables	2 presentations
24	European Open Science Cloud EOSC Symposium	21-23 October 2024	Berlin, Germany	EOSC community	1 participant
25	SENSEI Workshop	10 March 2025	Online	Project presentation	1 participant
26	EMSO ERIC Strategic Workshop	11-13 March 2025	Rome, Italy, online	Scientific and technology strategy	1 participant
27	OFC2025	30 March-3 April 2025	San Francisco, CA, USA	Sensing, meeting	1 participant
28	European Geosciences Union EGU	27 April-02 May 2025	Vienna, Austria, online	Geoscientists, including oceanography	4 presentations, 3 posters, booth
29	SubOptic 2025	2 - 5 June 2025	Lisbon, Portugal	Submarine cable industry, researchers	1 presentation
30	TNC25	9-13 June 2025	Brighton, UK	NRENs	3 presentations, 3 participants, training
31	IAGA-IASPEI - Early Career Scientist School	29 August 2025	Lisbon, Portugal	SoP / DAS	training, booth
32	IASPEI - Scientific sessions	1-5 September 2025	Lisbon, Portugal	Seismologists	5 presentations, 6 participants

No	Name of the event	Dates	Location	Focus/target stakeholders	Type of attendance
33	Nordunet Community Workshop	9–11 September 2025	Copenhagen, Denmark	NRENS	2 presentations
34	European Conference on Optical Communication ECOC	28 September-2 October 2025	Copenhagen, Denmark	Light Technologies	1 presentation, 2 participants
35	Research and Technology Infrastructures Summit	22-23 October 2025	Copenhagen-Denmark	Research and Technology Infrastructures	booth
36	Atlantic Convergence	28-30 October 2025	Lisbon, Portugal	Subsea, Data center, IX, Official bodies	1 participant
37	EPOS Seismology/ORFEUS workshop	24-27 November 2025	Athens, Greece	Seismologists	2 presentations
38	EMODnet Conference	25-26 November 2025	Brussels, Belgium	Oceanography	1 presentation, 1 participant
39	Digital Ocean Forum	27-28 November 2025	Brussels, Belgium	European Commission	2 participants
40	e-Infrastructure Reflection Group e-IRG workshop	9 December 2025	Amsterdam, Netherlands	e-Infrastructure	1 participant
41	Ocean Sciences Meeting OSM	22-27 February 2026	Glasgow, Scotland	Ocean Science	1 presentation
42	German Geophysical Society (DGG) Meeting	01-06 March 2026	Münster, Germany	Geophysics Scientific Community of Germany and Central Europe	1 presentation
43	Arctic Science Summit Week ASS	25 March-1 April 2026	Aarhus, Denmark	Arctic community	1 presentation

3.1.4 Cooperation with relevant projects

During SUBMERSE project implementation cooperation with relevant projects has been established. The scope of cooperation included sharing information about progress of the projects, participation in workshops and trainings organized by the partner projects. It should be mentioned that some of the SUBMERSE project partners are also involved in **GEANT GN5-2** and/or **Polar Connect** project which supports cooperation between the projects. Results obtained in one project are used by other partners, e.g. developed by SUBMERSE concept of Trusted Research Environment which defines principles for secure transfer, storage and access of data generated by the fibre sensing devices is widely accepted by other projects. Another example is sharing experience of installation and operation of instruments obtained in SUBMERSE to GEANT GN5-2 project for deployment of DAS in their infrastructure. Collaboration was made also between researchers of Smart European Networks for Sensing the Environment and Internet quality SENSEI.

In 2025, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed between SUBMERSE and **Blue-Cloud 2026** projects. The main objective is sharing experiences and skills about the development of both the Blue-Cloud's strategic roadmap and the SUBMERSE implementation pathways, as well as participation in the events organised by the partner project. As result of this cooperation, SUBMERSE project is setting up a VLAB as part of BLUE-CLOUD initiative.

Figure 2. Joint booth organized during IAGA–IASPEI Joint Scientific Meeting

During IAGA–IASPEI Joint Scientific Meeting on 1-5 September 2025 held in Lisbon SUBMERSE together with **Geo-INQUIRE**, European Plate Observing System and EMSO ERIC organised a booth to share information about the project, explore ideas and connect with colleagues across the community. For this event dissemination materials including short videos were developed and posted on project website and LinkedIn platform. At the booth an engaging talk was presented on the challenges and potential of the fibre-optic seafloor distributed sensors (see Figure above).

3.1.5 Conducted workshops and trainings

The objectives of training activities were i) to develop knowledge and skills required for the deployment and proper operation of fibre sensing instruments; and ii) to facilitate and support research groups working in different fields of Earth science in usage of the generated data. Detailed information about the training events performed by the project can be found in deliverable D4.4 Training report.

SUBMERSE training section was established on LifeWatch ERIC training platform based on Moodle learning management system. Training devoted to the introduction to State of Polarization analysis for seismic events monitoring is presented on [this platform](#). For internal and external participants, in-person DAS and SOP data training sessions were delivered in December 2024 and at IASPEI Early Career Scientists School in August 2025.

Furthermore, the SUBMERSE project, through partner GÉANT, organised dedicated **fibre sensing sessions** during research and education networking conferences TNC23, TNC24 and TNC25. This activity engaged GÉANT member NRENs who are operating fibre optic infrastructures in their countries and have close cooperation with research communities. Currently, more than 10 NRENs have already deployed or are planning to install fibre sensing instruments in their networks.

On 15-17 April 2026 the project organised a **community and final event**: “The future of subsea fibre-optic sensing from science to policy and society”. During the conference main achievements of the project in terms of deployed research instruments (8 permanent and 1 temporary deployments) and scientific results obtained from the generated data (more than 160 TB) were presented by the project participants. Five keynote presentations were made by the external researchers. Session of lightning 5 min. talks were conducted as well. The panel session “Research infrastructures: Unleashing the fibre sensing potential together” was organized with participation of the management of EMSO-EPOS-GÉANT-LifeWatch infrastructures. During the final event two trainings on GeoScience and Oceanographic applications were conducted for project internal and external participants. Figure below presents training in Oceanographic applications.

Figure 3. Community Event in Copenhagen

4 Conclusions

The stakeholder engagement and outreach activities carried out within the SUBMERSE project played an important role in ensuring the visibility, uptake and long-term sustainability of the project outcomes. Through structured engagement activities, the project successfully reached a diverse community of stakeholders including researchers, infrastructure providers, technology developers, relevant international and national organisations.

At the initial stage, a detailed identification of stakeholder groups was performed, which was slightly modified during the implementation of the project according to the project needs and ability to develop contact with relevant organizations. The stakeholder engagement process was strongly supported by the dissemination activities under Task 4.1 Communication and Dissemination, providing a systematic outreach and efficient messaging to the selected target groups. The diverse nature of stakeholder groups and their interests required close collaboration and coordination of all work packages. Engagement activities included: project website, social media, publications, presentations at conferences and workshops, conducted workshops and trainings, and access to generated datasets.

The main results of performed activities are following:

- Publication of over 5 research papers (5 already accepted and published, others under review)
- Participation and knowledge sharing at 43 international events with 37 presentations
- Established cooperation with 5 projects working on fiber sensing
- trainings conducted in Distributed Acoustic Sensing and State of Polarisation systems, and in GeoScience and Oceanographic applications
- Involvement of 3 new partners to the SUBMERSE project is also considered as a result of communication and engagement activities.

Overall, the stakeholder engagement activities carried out in the SUBMERSE project significantly contributed to the dissemination of knowledge, the promotion of fibre sensing technologies and the development of new collaborations across disciplines and sectors. These efforts support the long-term impact of the project by facilitating the integration of generated datasets, tools and expertise into future research, monitoring and innovation activities.

Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AGU	American Geophysical Union
D	Deliverable
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
e-IRG	e-Infrastructure Reflection Group
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EGU	European Geosciences Union
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
ESC	European Seismological Commission
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
IUGG	The International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics
NREN	National Research and Education Network
SENSEI	Smart European Networks for Sensing the Environment and Internet quality project
SOP	State of Polarisation
SSA	Seismological Society of America
SUBMERSE	SUBMarine cablEs for ReSearch and Exploration Definition project
T	Task
TNC	Research and education networking conference
WP	Work Package